

POSTBUCKLING PERFORMANCE OF A CO-CURED CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE AILERON

Murray L. Scott, Alan K.H. Cheung
Cooperative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures Ltd.
506 Lorimer Street, Fishermens Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia

ABSTRACT

The structure under study represents a typical aileron on a mid-size jet transport aircraft. A thin-buckling skin with multiple chordwise blade-stiffeners is a feature of this design. To achieve significant weight savings over the baseline, emphasis was placed on a thin-skinned postbuckling design. Co-curing the box structure eliminated the use of fasteners and pad-ups, which reduces weight and cost. A number of nonlinear analyses have been successfully conducted, showing MSC/NASTRAN to be an appropriate tool for analysing complex postbuckling structures. A weight saving for the control surface box structure of 34% was achieved.

INTRODUCTION

Stiffened panels in semi-monocoque construction have been extensively employed in metallic aerospace structures for many years. Incorporating postbuckling design concepts into such structures has further optimised their structural performance. However, the progressive introduction of advanced carbon fibre composites into aerospace structures presents new challenges in the design and manufacture of these components. Carbon fibre reinforced composites in honeycomb sandwich panels have now been widely used in control surfaces for commercial transport aircraft for well over a decade. Typical design configurations for components, such as ailerons incorporate carbon fibre/epoxy ribs and spars, which are mechanically fastened to honeycomb sandwich skins. Poor impact resistance, water ingress, skin/core delamination and costly repair of damaged skins are the most common causes of problems raised by operators of aircraft with this type of construction.

In recent years the imperative to reduce the cost of manufacturing advanced fibre composite components and wherever possible improve their operational performance has led to innovative design concepts being proposed, which do not rely on honeycomb sandwich construction techniques [1-2]. The most promising concept for the relatively lightly loaded components found in control surface structures is that characterised by thin integrally stiffened composite skins, which buckle below limit load levels in a similar manner to their metallic counterparts.

The design and manufacturing technology associated with composite/honeycomb sandwich panels was considered the baseline for the new composite control surface design presented in this paper. The structure under study represents a typical aileron on a mid-size jet transport aircraft. In order to demonstrate the weight and cost saving potential of thin buckling skins with integral blade-stiffening, a complete aileron has been designed which incorporates many innovative features. Central to this task was the selection of a one-piece composite manufacturing process which enabled the blade-stiffened skin, rear spar and ribs to be co-cured.

DESIGN PHILOSOPHY AND FEATURES

DESIGN OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives for the new design were as follows: to reduce the mass of the control surface box structure by 30%; to achieve or exceed existing requirements for quality, durability and damage tolerance; and to achieve existing requirements for environmental degradation and stiffness criteria.

DESIGN CONFIGURATION

The overall dimensions of the aileron are 2.8 m \times 0.4 m, with a local sweep angle of 16 degrees. There are four hinges supporting the aileron through its front spar. A 1.7 m long balance tab is located at the trailing edge extending from the inboard end of the structure. The aileron is actuated by a single control rod next to the inboard hinge. The baseline honeycomb structure has been redesigned by using thin buckling skins incorporating co-cured multi-blade-stiffeners [3]. There is a total of nine ribs and twelve stiffeners, which are positioned chordwise along the span as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Configuration of the control surface (Top surface not shown).

DESIGN FEATURES

To achieve significant weight savings over the honeycomb sandwich baseline structure, emphasis was placed on a thin-skinned postbuckling design. Buckling was only permitted in

the skins of the box structure. Front and rear spars, which carry the bending loads on the aileron, were designed not to buckle nor cripple at ultimate load. Some sections of the upper and lower skins however, were reinforced to prevent buckling. This was necessary to allow attachment of a fairing to the lower skin for the tab control rods, and skin strengthening at the critical areas. Multiple chordwise blade-stiffeners were incorporated to stiffen the thin buckling skin.

The aft box structure of the aileron, which includes the upper and lower skin, blade-stiffeners, rear spar and internal ribs, were co-cured. This eliminated the use of fasteners and pad-ups, and reduces weight and cost. The closure ribs and front spar were mechanically fastened to the box structure. This manufacturing method allows forward removal of the tooling [4].

Matching the stiffness of the baseline sandwich construction control surface was required. Since similar front and rear spars to the baseline control surface were used, bending stiffness has not been changed. Matching the torsional stiffness of the baseline control surface required a multi-rib structural design with the thin skins supported by multiple blade-stiffeners, as shown in Figure 2. The skin consists of two pairs of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies to resist the torsional loading and two 0° (spanwise plies) and one 90° (chordwise plies) to transfer the air loading to the surrounding structure. There are also local skin build-ups at the front and rear spars and around major hinge ribs.

Figure 2. Typical skin-stiffener interface.

Figure 3. Typical outboard stiffeners.

The blade-stiffeners had to be terminated or "run-out" at the front spar which required careful design to prevent stiffener disbonding. Local skin ply build-ups were used to inhibit skin buckling at the stiffener run-outs. All stiffening members were double flanged and blade "softening" or local blade ply "drop-offs" were incorporated to prevent buckling at the skin interface and reduce peel stresses. At the trailing edge and rear spar locations, the upper and lower surface blade-stiffeners join together forming a "semi-rib" which avoids stiffener run-outs and improves torsional stiffness as shown in Figure 3. The ribs were typically made from the similar web-skin interface as the stiffener, with two C-sections combined back-to-back forming an "I"-section. The inboard ribs were connected to the rear spar by wrapping the rib web towards the rear spar web to form a pair of rib flanges.

COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN/MANUFACTURE MODEL

CATIA was the Computer Aided Design and Manufacturing environment chosen for the project due to its extensive use in the aerospace industry. The CATIA design database was used as the sole design authority and was transferred digitally between the design centre in Melbourne and the manufacturing centre in Sydney.

A valuable feature is the Boolean capabilities of the CATIA solids. This algebraic management of solids allows the user to perform intersections, subtractions and additions. This technique was applied in the resulting geometry of the ribs, stiffeners and skins for each one of the control surface bays. The resulting solid is then the 3D model of the tool mandrel to be used for manufacturing, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Tool mandrels created by CATIA Boolean operations.

DESCRIPTION OF ANALYTICAL MODEL

LOADING CONDITIONS

In this study, two load cases were considered. The external loads were obtained as an extrapolation from the "11.2° Aileron Down" condition of a typical mid-size jet transport aircraft. A 2-D chordwise airload constantly distribution was obtained. In the finite element model, follower vector loads were applied to the top and bottom skins.

The second load case is the induced loading due to sympathetic bending of the wing. Enforced displacements were applied vertically downwards at the middle two hinges to simulate the radius of curvature induced by such wing bending. The critical load case is considered to be the combination of the above two cases.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The finite element (FE) model of the control surface was constructed using the pre- and post-processor P3/PATRAN. The model contains 14,000 four-noded quadrilateral elements and a total of 70,000 degrees of freedom. A 2-D orthotropic assumptions consistent with classical laminate theory was used.

In order to reduce the size of the model, blade-stiffeners were modelled using 2-D bar elements, as shown in Figure 5, where appropriate laminate properties were calculated and applied to the off-set bar elements. At the region where the stiffeners joined to form a "semi-rib" near the trailing edge and rear spar, shell elements were used. A minimum of six elements between stiffeners was used to effectively represent the half waves of the buckling skin. The control rod was fixed in all six degrees of freedom at the wing end, and the aileron was constrained to rotate about the hinge line.

DETAIL REGION

A refined mesh was used to model the critically loaded region near the actuator rod hinge. Blade-stiffeners were accurately modelled using shell elements allowing more detail to be included, enabling the stiffener run-out and ply build-ups/drop-offs to be incorporated. Modelling of the stiffeners correctly using shell elements, required at least four rows of elements along the height of the stiffener; otherwise, an artificially high stiffness will occur in the FE model for the stiffener [5]. The individual ply build-ups in the skin were also modelled for more accuracy, as was the actuator rod hinge including individual fasteners to provide a realistic load transfer from the aileron box structure.

Figure 5. Detail region of the finite element model
(Front spar and top skin not shown).

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The FE analysis package MSC/NASTRAN was used to perform the complex buckling analysis of the control surface structure. Linear buckling analysis using the Lanczos method in MSC/NASTRAN performs an eigensolution to predict the eigenvalues and eigenvectors, where buckling loads and their mode shapes can be determined. This enables the point of buckling to be defined and hence the buckling ratio (the ratio of ultimate load to buckling load) to be determined.

Geometric nonlinear analysis using the Modified Newton-Raphson method [6] was performed. The load was incremented by ten equal load steps and the stiffness matrix was updated automatically by MSC/NASTRAN. At each load step, an iterative method was used to derive the correct solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results presented are for the critical load case, which includes the enforced displacements for induced bending and the 2-D chordwise airload distribution. A linear static analysis of the aileron was conducted, where the computational run time was 24 minutes on an IBM RISC System/6000 Model 370 workstation. Results showed an outboard tip deflection of 52 mm at

ultimate load. Large out-of-plane deflections were encountered in the skins due to buckling and pressure loads. Since small deflections are assumed in linear analysis, membrane stiffening effects are not considered. The out-of-plane deflections are higher and the predicted stress levels are lower, hence the margins of safety are not conservative.

A linear buckling solution was also performed, where the computational run time was 1.7 hours. The first nine modes of buckling occurred at the outboard region due to its larger unsupported skin and wider stiffener pitch.

Finally, a geometric nonlinear analysis was performed. This analysis required 5.0 hours of computational run time to complete. The maximum deflection was 44 mm at the outboard tip, as shown in Figure 6. Complex compression/shear buckling of the top skin can be seen.

The deflections on the control surface versus the load for both linear and nonlinear analyses are shown in Figure 7. It should be noted that this graph is not end shortening versus load as is typical with results of nonlinear analyses. The tip deflection of the aileron is a function of the torsional stiffness of the structure and the bending stiffness of the ribs, stiffeners and rear spar. Up to the point of buckling, the tip deflection is the same for linear and nonlinear analyses. After the first buckling of the skins, the stiffness of the box structure changes, hence the difference in the linear and nonlinear analysis curves. The nonlinear load factor versus tip deflection curve indicates that the box structure increases in torsional stiffness after buckling, resulting in reduced tip deflections for a given load. A complex interaction of compression and shear buckling, combined with skin air-pressure loads occurs.

Figure 6. Deformed plot from nonlinear analysis.

Figure 7. Comparison between linear and nonlinear analysis.

Top Skin

Bottom Skin

Figure 8. Contour plot of buckling skin at ultimate load.

The out-of-plane displacements associated with the buckling of the skins at ultimate load are illustrated in Figure 8. Diagonal type shear buckling of the upper skin between stiffeners and ribs can be seen. Surface strain plots of critical elements at the top and bottom skins are shown in Figures 9 and 10; the results are extracted for the in-board skins near the actuator rib.

Figure 9. Load/shear-strain plot of critical element in the top skin.

Figure 10. Load/shear-strain plot of critical element in the bottom skin.

At load levels before buckling began, the outer surface of the top skin exhibited a higher strain than the inner surface under the same load factor (Refer Figure 9). This behaviour is due to the fact that load was applied by pressure in the direction towards the outer skin surface. However, at load levels after buckling, the buckling strain started to take over and the situation reversed. Similar behaviour is observed for the bottom skin (Refer Figure 10). However, since the pressure load was applied towards the inner surface, the inner skin surface constantly showed a higher strain when compared to the outer skin surface.

CONCLUSIONS

A number of geometric nonlinear analyses have been successfully conducted, showing MSC/NASTRAN to be an appropriate tool for analysing complex postbuckling structures. It is recommended that the full size static test of the aileron box structure be conducted as planned to verify the accuracy of the FE analyses. Expected weight savings have been realised with a 34% reduction being achieved for the control surface box structure. This leads to additional weight savings on the total control surface due to the reduction of concentrated weights required for balancing. The manufacturing costs are currently being evaluated and are reported elsewhere [4]. It is concluded that this postbuckling composite control surface design shows good potential as a more efficient alternative for the next generation of transport aircraft.

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